

INCREASING SINGLE SKILLS IN THE EMPTY RAW HANDS THROUGH AUDIOVISUAL MEDIA

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Abstract:

This research was motivated by the decline in the achievements of regional athletes of the Indonesian Pencak Silat Association (IPSI). Tangerang district, in Banten Province Fifth Regional Student Sports Week Championship, in 2016. This study is to determine whether the use of audio-visual media can improve the athletes' skills of Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong (Solo Routine Without the Use of the Weapons) at the training area of the IPSI of Tangerang district. The main idea of this study uses the Kurt Lewin Model, for Action: Planning; Action; Observation; and Reflection which was carried out in two (2) cycles. In this research, 20 (twenty) athletes from IPSI Tangerang district participated in the training. The focus of this research is to improve the skills of the Solo Routine Without the Use of the Weapons performed by those athletes. The technique of collecting data through action tests is by observing the athletes through the use of audiovisual media. Data analysis techniques were carried out in qualitative and quantitative descriptive method The results from the two cycles of actions, observations and reflections, showed that the Solo Routine Without the Use of the Weapons skills through audio visual media had increased From the results of the first cycle test, 8 athletes (40 % of the percentage) showed the correct moves of the Solo Routine Without the Use of the Weapons, while the other 12 athletes (60% of the percentage) still made the wrong moves. The results of the second cycle test showed 14 athletes (70% of the percentage) did the right moves and 6 athletes (30% from the percentage) still made the wrong moves. Based on the results of the above research, it is evident that there was a 30 % increase in the skills of the athletes in the second cycle rather than the first cycle The results showed that the usage of audio visual media in training of the Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong (Solo Routine Without the use of the Weapons) can improve the skills of athletes in the training facility at the Tangerang District Indonesian Pencak Silat Association.

Penelitian ini dilatarbelakangi oleh menurunnya prestasi para atlet daerah Ikatan Pencak Silat Indonesia (IPSI), kabupaten Tangerang dalam Kejuaraan Pekan Olahraga Pelajar Daerah V provinsi Banten, tahun 2016. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui apakah penggunaan media audio visual dapat meningkatkan keterampilan Gerak Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong di pelatihan daerah binaan IPSI kabupaten Tangerang. Desain Penelitian Tindakan ini menggunakan Model Kurt Lewin, yaitu: Perencanaan; Tindakan; Pengamatan; dan Refleksi, yang dilaksanakan dalam dua (2) siklus. Adapun sampel penelitian meliputi para atlet binaan pelatihan daerah IPSI kabupaten Tangerang yang berjumlah 20 orang. Fokus penelitian adalah dengan meningkatkan keterampilan Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong yang dilakukan oleh para atlet. Teknik pengumpulan data melalui tes perbuatan yang diamati

melalui penggunaan media audio visual. Teknik analisis data dilakukan secara deskriptif kualitatif dan kuantitatif Hasil penelitian dari dua siklus, menunjukkan bahwa pengamatan atas keterampilan Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong melalui media audio visual mengalami peningkatan. Dari hasil test siklus pertama, 8 atlet (40% dari persentase) menunjukkan kebenaran gerak Jurus Baku Tunggal Tangan Kosong sedangkan 12 atlet (60 % dari persentase lainnya masih melakukan movement yang salah. Hasil tes siklus kedua menunjukkan 14 atlet (70% dari persentase) melakukan movement yang benar dan 6 atlet (30% ari persentase) masih melakukan movement yang salah. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian tersebut diatas, terbukti bahwa terjadi peningkatan sebesar 30% keterampilan para atlet di siklus kedua daripada siklus pertama. Dari hasil penelitian ini dapat disimpulkan bahwa pelatihan Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong melalui media audio visual dapat meningkatkan keterampilan para atlet binaan Ikatan Pencak Silat Indonesia kabupaten Tangerang.

Keywords: Pencak Silat; Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong; Media Audio Visual.

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1. Introduction

The results of observations in the field are related to the decreasing achievement of the regional training team of the youth of the Indonesian Pencak Silat Association (IPSI) in Tangerang district in single, multiple and team categories, especially single in the POPDA V Banten Province competition in 2016. Results of discussions with judges there are a number of motion truths that are not in accordance with the moves that are contested and the lack of stability of the movement as for the results of the discussion with the trainers of various obstacles encountered. The factor that causes the decline in achievement is the medium of training and the standard single practice training session.

Of the Jurus Tunggal Baku Tangan Kosong (Solo Routine Without the use of the Weapons) that are competed at both the regional and international levels. This is explained in the competition rules book Indonesian Pencak Silat Association (IPSI, 2012), that: "A single category is a category that shows a fighter demonstrating his skill in a single, correct, precise and steady, full of inspiration, empty-handed and armed and subject to regulations that apply to single categories".

2. Exercise

Achievement and quality of athletes in various sports must be increased, so as not to decrease (Nedianto, 2016). Achievement of achievement is the result of a systematic planned training process and increased training load. Exercise according to harsono (Tangkudung & Wahyuningtyas, 2006) explains that exercise is a systematic process and practice that is done repeatedly with more days increasing the amount of training load and intensity of the exercise. Tangkudung (Amrullah, 2015) explains the purpose of the exercise, among others, to help athletes improve the skills of their sporting achievements in obtaining and perfecting selected sports

techniques, refining and perfecting strategies, instilling the quality of willingness, ensuring and securing optimal team preparation, to achieve and expand physical development thoroughly, to maintain a state of health. According to Bompa (Widiastuti & Reny, 2017: 5) said that training is to achieve the goal of improving the organization's system and its function to optimize sports performance or performance. According to M. Sajoto, (Aprilia, Kristiyanto, & Doewes, 2018) physical conditions in the human body consist of ten components including: 1) Strength (strength), 2) Endurance (endurance), 3) Muscle power (musculus power) , 4) Speed (speed), 5) Flexibility (flexibility), 6) Agility (7), 7) Coordination (coordination), 8) Balance (balance), 9) Accuracy (accuracy), 10) Reaction (reaction) . Bompa stated that "training must be organized and planned so that it can guarantee the achievement of the objectives of the training. The training planning process shows that it is well organized, so that it can help athletes to achieve better results based on their training and achievements. "From the outline in general the exercise is a planned and systematic exercise to increase physical development with the amount of training load and increasing intensity (Sejati, Tomi, & Purnami, 2017). The opinion of Budiwanto (Langga & Supriyadi, 2016) that, "training is the process of carrying out sports activities carried out based on a systematic program of training, aimed at increasing the athlete's ability to achieve as much as possible, especially in preparation for a match". This exercise has many elements, which aim to improve the quality of training participants or athletes in developing talents and promoting science that can be accounted for related to sports coaching.

3. Pencak Silat

The Pencak Silat Association throughout Indonesia (IPSI) is the parent of the Pencak Silat organization in Indonesia. On May 18, 1948 in Solo (before the first PON), the warriors Gathered and formed the organization of the Indonesian Pencak Silat Association (IPSSI). The first general chairman of IPSSI is Mr. Wongsonegoro. Then renamed the Indonesian Pencak Silat Association (IPSI) (Kriswanto, 2015), in the Indonesian dictionary (KBBI, 2016) pencak silat is defined as a game (skill) in defending itself with the ability to fend off, attack and defend themselves with or without weapons. Cultural heritage of the ancestors of the Indonesian Pencak Silat nation includes sports that are competed both at the regional, national and international levels. De Castella's research shows that martial arts can build self-esteem, teach how to deal with opposition and aggression (Mardotillah: & Zein, 2016). Many benefits obtained in pencak silat learning, such as the development of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor Mulyana (Marwan, 2018). According to johansyah (Widiastuti & Mulyani, 2017) pencak silat is a sport that consists of attitude (position) and movement - movement (movement). The basic movement of pencak silat is a planned, directed, coordinated and controlled movement.

Pencak silat matches are divided into several categories, Pencak Silat match categories consist of: 1) match categories, 2) single categories, 3) multiple categories, and 4) team categories (Kriswanto, 2015). Similar things According to johansyah (Widiastuti & Mulyani, 2017) in a pencak silat match the basic techniques are not all used and played in accordance with the applicable provisions and categories contested. This category is a single, double and team match category.

4. **Jurus Tunggal Baku (Single Category)**

The single category or commonly referred to as a single category is one of the categories that are always contested in every pencak silat event. The single category is a category of pencak silat matches that showcase seatletters demonstrating their proficiency in a single stance in a correct, precise, and steady manner full of empty handed and armed johansyah (Spyanawati, 2014). The categories are match, single, double and team categories. In the pencak silat competition there are two categories that must be contested are: 1) Match Category and 2) Art Category which is divided into: a) single category or often called pencak silat single stance art, b) multiple categories, and c) team. George (2006: 17) The performance of pencak silat TGR numbers is emphasized on aesthetic values with the aim of demonstrating the beauty and harmony of martial arts by not ignoring ethical, technical and athletics values.

Johansyah (2004) in his book explains that the single category of pencak silat is pencak silat which displays a fighter seatlet demonstrating its proficiency in a single standard manner correctly, precisely and steadily full of inspiration with empty or armed hands.

A single category is a category that displays the fighter seatlet demonstrating its proficiency in a single, standard manner correctly, precisely and steadily, full of inspiration, empty-handed and armed and subject to the rules and regulations that apply to a single category (Munas, 2012). Athletes must display their moves in an orderly manner starting with their bare hands, machete moves and ending with a skill move with skill and correctness for three (3) minutes.

A single skill is a complex form of skill consisting of various kinds of moves and moves both empty hand and weapon. In a single stance, the standard stance consists of 7 bare-hand moves, 3 machetes, and 4 strokes of sticks or toads, with a performance time of 3 minutes. From starting the gong the initial sign starts with the final gong being sounded, the fighter must do a series of moves in accordance with the provisions.

5. **Media**

Technological progress is something that cannot be avoided in this life, because technological progress will run in accordance with the progress of science (Ngafifi, 2014). (Putro, 2017) Products from communication and information technology are mass media where currently developing rapidly and constantly, on the other hand, this inspires us to see the media as the center of cultural orientation for modern Western capitalism (Setiawan, 2018). Media is a means or tool to convey information in the form of audio and visual. Media comes from the word Medium meaning ("between") the term refers to anything that carries information between a source and recipient (SIDI & MUKIMAN, 2016). According to Jatmiko (2016) and Sidi (2016) explain there are six basic categories of media, namely: 1) Text, 2) Audio, 3) Visual, 4) video, 5) television, 6) Engineering (manipulative) (objects). According to Bretz (Sadiman, AS, R, & et. Al., 2002) distinguish between broadcast media (telecommunication) and recording media so that there are eight media classifications: (1) audio-visual motion media, (2) silent audio-visual media, (3) semi-motion visual media, (4) visual motion media, (5) stationary video media, (6) semi-motion media, (7) audio media, and (8) print media. According to Sanaky Hujair (2010) Audio visual media is a set of tools that can project moving and audible images. The blend between image and sound forms

the same character as the original object. Tools included in the category of audio visual media are television, VCD, sound slides, and films. In the development of this video-shaped media, after the video program is finished, the results can be displayed via Video Compact Disk (VCD). In the opinion of Kustandi and Sutjipto (Hardianti & Asri, 2017) adding weaknesses in video media, namely: 1) the procurement of video media requires very expensive costs and a lot of time; 2) when playing video images and sounds will continue; 3) not all students are able to follow the information conveyed through video media".

6. Audio Visual

Audio visual media is media that has sound elements and image elements. This type of media has a better ability, because it covers both types of auditive (listening) and visual media (viewing) (Ardyanto, 2018). In Sanaky Hujair. (lestari, Halimahtusha'diah, & Fibria, 2018) explains, a set of tools that can project moving and sound images, such tools as active PC-speakers, VCDs and sound slide media. According to Hamdani, visual media is media that can be seen using the sense of sight. According to Wina Sanjaya (Purwono, Yutmini, & Anita, 2014) "Audio-visual media are media that have sound elements and elements of images that can be seen, such as video recordings, slides, sounds, etc.". This explains the audio visual and video media is a tool to convey information well. Natoli explained "stressed that audio-visual materials are important in the teaching and learning processes because "Having seen something, most people remember, for whatever that thing was, it conjures up an image at a mere mention and can be talked about freely" emphasizing that audio-visual material is important in the teaching and learning process because "After seeing something, most athletes remember, for whatever it is the image appears with a designation and (Ashaver & Igyuve, 2013). Audio-visual motion media is the appropriate modern instructional media with the development of science and technology, this media includes vision, hearing and displaying moving image elements, such as moving video and film (Selvia, 2014). In this study using audio-visual motion media or videos that have sound and image elements.

7. Characteristics of Adolescents

Adolescence is a period that experiences the most changes psychologically, biologically and physiologically (Hartini, 2017). According to Wirawan (Putro, 2017). The World Health Organization (WHO) sets limits on who is conceptually teenagers. He stated by WHO there are three criteria used; biological, psychological, and socio-economic, namely: (1) the individual who develops when he first shows his secondary sexual signs until he reaches sexual maturity, (2) individuals who experience psychological development and identification patterns from children to adulthood, and (3) a transition from full socio-economic dependence to a more independent situation. Atkinson's opinion (Nisya & Sofiah, 2012) that, adolescence is a transition period or a transition period from childhood to adulthood. Kuhlen and Thompson (Murni, 2017) suggest that individual physical development includes four aspects, namely: a. The nervous system that greatly influences the development of intelligence and emotions; b. The muscles that affect the development of motor strength and ability; c. Endoktrin gland, which causes the emergence of new behavioral patterns, such as at the age of adolescents develop feelings of pleasure to be active in an activity that some members consist of the opposite sex; d. Physical structure / body which includes height and proportion. According to Soebroto (Karyono & Kriswanto, 2006) ages 9 to 10 years are a mature age for the development of children to enter the next training, which is between

the ages of 13 and 16 years. Monks et al (Lidya and Diah, 2012) Adolescence clearly shows the traits of the transition or transition period, because adolescents have not yet obtained the status of adult athletes but no longer have children's status. Global adolescence takes place at ages 12 to 21 years, with a division of 12 to 15 years is early adolescence, 15 to 18 years are middle adolescence, and 18 to 21 years are late adolescence. Adolescence (adolescence) is a period of transition from children to adults. In this period various changes occurred both hormonal, physical, psychological and social changes. This change occurs very quickly and sometimes without us knowing it (Batubara, 2010). According to Waharsono (Rezki, 2016) states, "In line with increasing body size and increasing physical ability, it also increases the ability of the movement". According to the description it can be concluded that adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood marked by changes in body shape, psychological and emotional. According to Awi Muhadi Wijaya (Rismayanthi, 2013) childhood is often referred to as the ideal time to learn motor skills for the following reasons: (1) The child's body is more flexible than the adult athlete's body so that the child is easier to master motor skills. (2) Children do not have many skills that will collide with the skills they have just learned, so children will learn new skills more easily. (3) Overall, children are more courageous to try when they are younger than after being big. Therefore they dare to try something new, giving rise to the motivation needed to learn. (4) Children like repetition, so they are willing to repeat the action until the muscles are trained to do it effectively. (5) Children have more time to learn motor skills. This study focuses on adolescent athletes where the period of cognitive development and motion continues to increase.

8. Research Methodology

This study uses action research methods (Action Research). Sudjana stated that action research is collecting, processing, analyzing and deducing data obtained from certain types of actions that are intentionally designed and used to see the effectiveness of these actions (Sudjana, 2010). This action research (Action Research) uses the research design model of Kemmis and McTaggart in the form of a cycle or round of activities which includes the following stages:

1) Planning

Compile Planning that is mature in research needs to be done after we know the problem in practice. this aims to find out what is needed in the study. so that research becomes effective, efficient and on target.

2) Actions (Action)

Follow-up of results Planning must be realized by the action (Action) of the researcher in the form of any effort that must be done on the research so that the results of the planning can run in accordance with what is expected then applied to the research subject.

3) Observation (Observing)

The next stage is the observation (observing) of the research both on the implementation process and the results obtained during the study.

4) Reflection (Reflecting)

Reflection is the final series after observation in research, in this case the researcher can conclude what things have happened in the research process.

9. Discussions

The results of observations and data analysis in Cycle I were obtained showing 60% of the total participants who had a value of less than 25 per cent of the movement of a single hand empty hand and 40% above the truth of the motion.

Table 1: Data Distribution of Cycle I observation results

No	Value Jurus Tangan Kosong	Frequency	%
1.	1 – 24 movement	8	40%
2.	25 – 50 movement	12	60%
Jumlah		20	100%

The results of the analysis of the observation cycle II obtained the correct total movement of 547 from 20 participants for the correct value of the average movement 27.15 the maximum value of the movement maximum 35 and the minimum value of movement 16. Participants who were declared complete numbered 6 participants while the value of participants who declared total 14 participants. Data is described in the following table:

Table 2: Data Distribution of Cycle II observation results

No	Value Jurus Tangan Kosong	Frequency	%
1.	1 – 24 movement	6	30 %
2.	25 – 50 movement	14	70 %
Jumlah		20	100 %

Figure 2. Cycle II Histogram

The results of observations and analysis of the data obtained showed that 70% of the total participants who had the truth value of motion in the first cycle were only 40% of the truth of the motion of a single hand empty, there was a 30% increase in the truth of the motion. For more details, comparison of cycle I and cycle II can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Data Distribusi Siklus I dan Siklus II

No	Value jurus tangan kosong	CYCLE I		CYCLE II	
		F	%	F	%
1.	1–24 movement	12	60 %	6	30 %
2.	25–50 movement	8	40 %	14	70 %
Jumlah		20	100 %	20	100 %

The results of this study indicate that the application of audio-visual media to improve the motion skills of Jurus Tunggak Baku Tangan Kosong, standard hand can be used as a medium for practicing Jurus Tunggak Baku Tangan Kosong for adolescent athletes training in the Tangerang District of Pencak Silat. So the recommendations for trainers by preparing the media and the means to practice athletes are active and passionate about practicing.

10. Conclusions

Based on the description of the implementation of the research and observations carried out, it was concluded that the application of audio-visual media to improve the motion skills of standard single-handed moves can be used as one of the media to practice the standard blank hand moves for youth athletes training in the Pencak Silat sports branch in Tangerang District.

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